

WAYS OF IMPLEMENTING INTERDISCIPLINARY CONNECTIONS IN TEACHING THE TOPICS OF "ELECTRIC CHARGE" AND "ELECTRIC RESISTANCE" IN THE 7TH GRADE

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Abstract. *This article expresses the opinions about the new pedagogical technologies offered in the educational system. At the same time, it was emphasized the importance of a comprehensive approach to education and training of schoolchildren based on interdisciplinary relations and their elements and an important factor of implementation. The teaching of physics in interdisciplinary connection and thereby ensuring the harmony of knowledge is shown on the example of the topics "Electric charge" and "Electric resistance" of the 7th grade physics course of general secondary schools.*

Keywords: *physics teaching methodology, interdisciplinary relations, quality of education, knowledge of electricity, electric charge, electrical resistance, development of interdisciplinary relations.*

Introduction. In the interdisciplinary teaching of physics in the countries of the world, the effective use of modern educational methods in the development of the teacher's knowledge of the physics course and related subjects and the improvement of the educational process is considered as one of the main issues, and many research works in this field done. Using innovative methods in the interdisciplinary interactive teaching of the physics course and applying it to the process of physics education, forming (creating) didactic support and ways to develop the physical worldview (thinking) of students and developing interdisciplinary interactive teaching technologies through its development special attention is paid to improvement.

Based on the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 19, 2021 "On measures to increase the quality of education in the field of physics and develop scientific research" PR-5032, to increase the quality of education in Physics and a comprehensive program of measures to ensure the effectiveness of scientific research in the field of physics [1] was approved. According to it, the following tasks were defined:

- improving the quality of teaching physics in schools;
- improvement of textbooks and training manuals;
- development of the system of training, retraining and professional development of personnel in physics, in particular, teachers of schools in rural areas;
- wide implementation of information and communication technologies in the educational process;
- to increase the level of inclusion of young people in physical education by introducing personnel training in new and high-demand specialties in the educational market;

ensuring the integral connection of scientific research in the field of physics with production.

Methods. The new pedagogical technologies offered in the following years, their elements and any research to be carried out are compatible with life, provide independent work and research of the student, serve to meet the needs of education, science and production, and train personnel who create new improved technologies. In particular, the work that should be carried out in the process of physics education, that is, the methods that should be taken into account in the methodology of teaching physics, should be constantly looked at from the point of view of the requirements of the time.

Application, development, consolidation and generalization of knowledge and skills acquired by students from other subjects should be reflected in the tasks of teaching. In the content of the educational material, it is necessary to pay special attention to issues that require relying on previously acquired knowledge (from other subjects), as well as to issues that develop in the teaching of subsequent subjects.

In general, such an approach to learning concepts develops students' thinking, helps to form their abilities such as comparing, analyzing different facts, drawing conclusions and conclusions, and helps them to creatively approach solving problems in their independent activities.

Discussions. Interdisciplinary relations are an important condition and result of a comprehensive approach to education and upbringing of schoolchildren. Providing knowledge in only one subject can limit the possibility of a methodical and creative approach to the teacher. Every teacher-pedagogue realizes that the success of a lesson, lecture, conversation, as well as any educational event depends on the creation of activity in the acquisition of multifaceted knowledge (in the educational process), regardless of what kind of educational institution he works in. should be enough.

The formation of interest that ensures the active participation of students is the most important factor in achieving the quality of education. Creation of educational projects, participation in innovative projects, participation in clubs, competitive courses increases their need for knowledge, makes the educational process more meaningful. Due to the practical application of the knowledge obtained from other fields of science, their skills are further developed and become vitally important. Physical knowledge enriches the scientific worldview of schoolchildren, provides them with concrete material, and is later used to form scientific concepts and generalized knowledge in extracurricular activities, to reveal scientific laws. Interdisciplinarity in general secondary education is a clear expression of the integration processes taking place in the life of science and society today. These connections are important for students' acquisition of practical and scientific-theoretical knowledge and skills. With the help of interdisciplinary relations, a basis is created for the comprehensive identification of complex multifaceted problems of reality, approach to the problem and its solution [2].

It is important and necessary to connect complementary disciplines. Academic subjects included in this category: drawing, computer science, physics, mathematics, technology, chemistry, biology, etc. significantly increase the level of understanding and in-depth study.

The role and importance of teaching physics and electricity in the work of physics teachers should be explained based on the fact that using and saving electricity is an integral part of our daily life. Because the lights, televisions, refrigerator, iron, computer and many other household appliances in our house are powered by electricity. Since production technologies work on

electricity, in order to develop students' innovative ideas, it is necessary to teach the topics of the school's physics course in an interdisciplinary manner and thereby ensure the harmony of knowledge.

Educational manuals and methodological instructions, electronic software, lesson plans on topics, methods of demonstrating experiments aimed at increasing the effectiveness of teaching by identifying the specific features of the relationship of the laws of electricity with other subjects in the school physics course, It is appropriate to develop and recommend for the educational process, such as creating slides. Materials in the form of a table are of great importance in ensuring that the knowledge provided is understandable to the students and in the implementation of the goal, in the correct organization of connections and visibility.

Results. When teaching the topic of electric charge [3], we recommend interdisciplinary teaching with relevant knowledge of history, chemistry, natural sciences, informatics and information technologies (Table 1).

Table 1

Electric power			
History	Chemistry	Natural sciences	Informatics and IT
In 1750, Benjamin Franklin created a simple theory of electricity. He introduced the concept of positive and negative charge for the first time.	An atom of a substance consists of a positively charged nucleus and a negatively charged electron. Therefore, positive and negative ions are formed in electrolytes.	Solar panels generate electricity from the sun's energy. The energy produced by these solar panels is developing and increasing year by year.	A computer monitor is made of plasma, which consists of positive and negative ions, so we need to protect it from damage.

Table 2

Electrical resistance		
Mathematics	Natural sciences	Informatics and IT
Operations on fractions are used in calculations. $\frac{R_a}{R_m} = \frac{\rho_a}{\rho_m} = 1.48$ When aluminum and copper conductors are the same size, the resistance of aluminum is 1.48 times greater than the resistance of copper.	Cho'g'lanma lampochkaning quvvati 60 W, LED lampochkaning quvvati 10 W bo'lsa ikkalasining yoritilganligi bir xil bo'lgani uchun LED lampochkasi 6 barobar energiyani tejaydi.	Calculation of the diameter of the conductor using "C++", Python and other electronic programs when solving problems related to the calculation of the capacity of the production enterprise and preparing innovative developments.

When studying the topic of electrical resistance, explaining to students that the resistance of substances depends on the size of the conductor, the relative resistance, comparing the resistance of conductors of the same size, using an electronic program to calculate the consumption power when connecting production enterprises to the electrical network taking into account that we should choose the correct diameter of the conductor, then to save more energy, the law of

electricity and the history of the discovery of phenomena and teaching in interdisciplinary communication will guide students to create new technologies (Table 2) and innovative ideas develop [4].

Conclusion. The importance of the use of modern pedagogical technologies, interdisciplinary communication and ensuring the active participation of students in the educational process was emphasized. New methods and approaches, as well as the integration of knowledge from other disciplines, help to develop students' ability to think independently. In the process of physics education, electricity and its importance in life are especially important. It is necessary for teachers to improve the quality of education by strengthening interdisciplinary relations and making educational materials meaningful and interesting in the development of innovative ideas. New technologies, methodological guides and interactive materials used in the educational process can make the learning process of students more effective and interesting. Thus, modern approaches to education are important in enriching students' scientific and practical skills. In addition, imparting knowledge in only one subject can limit the possibility of a methodical and creative approach to the teacher. Of course, the level of implementation of these proposed recommendations and their effectiveness will depend on the teacher's knowledge, level of knowledge of related subjects and his qualifications. Interdisciplinary connections increase the content of knowledge at scientific-theoretical and educational-educational levels and activate the student's mental activity [5-13]. Based on the above, we believe that it is appropriate to constantly implement and develop interdisciplinary relations.

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